

Voltammetric studies of 2-amino-4-(2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine

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Optimum conditions have been established for carrying out voltammetry at glassy carbon electrode for the anticancer drug 2-amino-4-(2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine. The quantitative determination in terms of peak current magnitude (I_p) in microamperes (μA) is found to be the best in 0.125 molar aqueous sodium carbonate buffer when GCE was held at -0.05 V for a period of 60 s and then scanned at the rate of 50 mV s^{-1} . Voltammogram shows two peaks at -1.39 V and -1.54 V (E_p values). Differential pulse polarography has also been carried out and 4-electron stepwise reduction is observed for the system in alkaline medium.

The present communication reports establishment of voltammetric methodology under optimum conditions of pH, ionic strength of supporting electrolyte, rate of potential scan etc. for 2-amino-4-(2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (AHCPPP) that has been reported to show anticancer activity¹. The repeated voltammetric results were further treated statistically and also the standard calibration curve was constructed for this system.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation of variables : The first cyclic scan gave a good peak current for both the peaks, however further non-stop multiple cyclic scans resulted in fall in peak current value successively, suggesting either desorption of specie from the electrode surface as time passed or formation of a non-electroactive product². Thus it was the first scan that gave actual value of the determination and hence conditions were optimised for the first scan voltammogram peaks.

Significant enhancement of peak current resulted from selecting optimum pH of supporting electrolyte³. Various aqueous buffers used were potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.0), acetate (pH 5.5), phosphate (pH 7.6), borate (pH 9.2) and carbonate (pH 11.0). Maximum peak current was obtained only in carbonate buffer. Hence for further work, carbonate buffer was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Ionic strength of the supporting electrolyte also affected the magnitude of I_p ³. Carbonate buffer solutions of various ionic strength were employed keeping drug quantity the same, and I_p was found highest in 0.125 M carbonate buffer. This solution parameter is characteristic of each compound analysed⁴ and for further observations 0.125 M was decided to be the optimum ionic strength for this system. The drug solution in optimum pH and buffer strength was scanned at varying values of scan rates ($10\text{ to }80\text{ mV s}^{-1}$). I_p was found highest at 50 mV s^{-1} and this scan rate was maintained for

further investigations.

The GCE was immersed in drug solution and held at a voltage known as accumulation voltage (AV) prior to its scanning². Various AV values were employed between $-0.39\text{ to }-1.25\text{ V}$. Current was found to be maximum when held at -0.50 V . A series of accumulation time periods (AT) were given to GCE prior to scan (30 to 900 s) and highest I_p was obtained at AT = 60 s.

Thus the voltammetry of AHCPPP in terms of its I_p value magnitude was carried out using 0.125 molar aqueous carbonate buffer of pH 11.0 when GCE was held at -0.50 V for 60 s and then scanned the potentials at the rate of 50 mV s^{-1} .

Voltammetric signal showed two peaks; first peak was obtained at -1.39 V and the second one appeared at -1.54 V which seems to be the characteristic peak potentials E_v or E_p during stepwise reduction as predicted from the polarographic (DPP) study for the same system. These peaks were obtained during negative scan, i.e. when the electrode was being made reducing and hence they are reducing peaks⁶. On reverse scan, i.e. during positive scan no peak appeared, thus indicating non-reversible nature of the electrode process⁷. Similar conclusions have been reported by earlier workers^{7,8}. Further, when differential pulse polarography (DPP) was carried out of the same drug system, the value of n (number of electron change) was ascertained to be $n = 4$, using Kroon-De Vries method⁵ from which four-electron reduction may be predicted⁹.

With the established optimum conditions, repeated voltammograms were obtained for exactly the same concentration of fresh drug solution taken each time and I_p for both the peaks was recorded respectively to observe the reproducibility. Fairly constant I_p values suggest satisfactory reproducibility of the determination. Mean, range, mean

deviation, variance, standard deviation, 95% confidence limits and confidence interval values calculated are respectively 2.4, 0.4, 0.066, 0.016, 0.126, (+2.532), (-2.268) and 0.264 respectively, expressing a good level of accuracy and precision for use in determination studies.

A standard calibration curve was plotted for this system. The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) calculated⁶ for this curve has a value of +0.9483, suggesting a satisfactory linearity between I_p and concentration, and therefore reliability in its use for determination of unknown concentration. This curve was also found to show a good effective concentration range.

Experimental

The instrument used was BAS CV-27 voltammograph with X-Y recorder. The 3-electrode system consisted of BAS MF-2012 glassy carbon indicator electrode, saturated calomel as reference electrode with platinum wire as auxiliary electrode. An Elico LI 10-T pH meter with combined electrode was used.

The buffers and double-distilled solvents (Excel, A.R.) were used. Water used was triple-distilled. All chemicals used were AnalaR grade.

AHCPP compound was synthesised by the reported method¹ and its purity was checked by m.p. and tlc.

General procedure : Initially the CV-27 alongwith X-Y recorder and the 3-electrode system was activated by triangular voltage sweeps¹⁰. Electrode activity was tested using solution of ferricyanide-ferrocyanide system in aq. KCl¹¹. Voltammogram so obtained was compared with the standard voltammogram¹² for the above system and thus instrument was standardised.

The GCE was immersed in 10^{-3} M drug solution held at a fixed known voltage (AV) for a pre-determined time (AT). After this the potential scan was employed in cyclic manner where initially the voltage was increasingly reducing and then the scan was reversed in opposite direction¹³. Signal in the form of one or more peak or peaks appeared at a voltage value at which the drug specie was showing electroactivity, i.e. getting oxidised or reduced. The signal was reported in terms of peak current values in microamperes (μ A)

and further parameters were optimised with a view to obtain highest I_p value.

Electrode was regenerated by repeated scanning in clean water^{8,14}, followed by polishing with buff cloth and 0.05 μ m alumina slurry in water¹⁴. In addition, depolarisation of electrode was done when the electrode was held in clean water at different potentials for 2 min¹⁵ and it was also given subsequent scans at opposing voltages¹⁶ to bring about depolarisation of any specie accumulated at the electrode surface. Combination of repeated scanning, polishing and depolarisation in regular fashion was found to give regenerated surface that gave reproducible results.

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